

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 2

ESDM-based CDOs, data tools and visualisation applications

Milestone MS11

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1. Introduction

This report linked to milestone MS11 documents the final software release of the ESDM-enabled post-processing, analytics and visualisation (PAV) applications providing links and pointers to the released code. These include: CDO, Ophidia and ParaView.

The integration of ESDM with CDO, data and visualisation tools was achieved mainly by relinking or recompiling the software with the ESDM-NetCDF version developed in WP4, with minor code modifications. In the case of Ophidia a more tight integration has been evaluated by using the ESDM API [1]. Besides the integration with ESDM, the key developments from the project included in the last release of the PAV use cases comprise: analytical kernels (GPU-based, in-flight), better support for ESIWACE2 flagship model grids, in-situ visualisation approaches, etc.

The envisioned developments and improvements on the post-processing, analytics and visualisation tools have been released and included in the main software branches. Deliverable D5.3 will report more in detail the key development activities for the selected PAV applications.

2. Ophidia

Ophidia is a CMCC Foundation research effort addressing Big Data challenges for eScience [3]. The Ophidia framework is an open source (GPLv3) solution for the analysis of scientific multi-dimensional data, mainly targeted at climate science applications, although it has also been successfully exploited in other scientific domains (e.g., seismology, biology, fire prevention).

The main developments in the project include: the integration with the ESDM API and the development of a specific set of new operators to interface ESDM data [1], improvements in the data loading features to better support the project datasets, adaptations for the ESDM-PAV integration and extensions for in-flight analytical kernels [2].

All the developments reported above from the project have been included in the latest release of the Ophidia framework at the time of the writing of this document (v1.7).

The source code is available on the GitHub repository <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/>. In particular, the last release (source code tars and RPM/DEB binaries) of the main Ophidia components can be accessed at:

- Ophidia IO server: <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/ophidia-io-server/releases>
- Ophidia analytics framework: <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/ophidia-analytics-framework/releases>
- Ophidia front-end server: <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/ophidia-server/releases>

Moreover, in the context of the project, the overall setup procedure of the Ophidia framework has been simplified and the software has been included in the list of packages available through Spack (e.g.,

https://spack.readthedocs.io/en/latest/package_list.html#ophidia-analytics-framework). A container image has also been created with all the Ophidia development to support users during training events (<https://hub.docker.com/r/ophidiabigdata/ophidia-training>) [4].

The binaries linked in GitHub include most of the developments from the project, however it is worth mentioning that, in order to enable the ESDM-based extensions, specific options have to be used at build time [1]. The ESDM-based kernels can also be enabled at compilation time [2]. The last release of the kernels can be found at: <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/esdm-pav-analytical-kernels>.

3. CDO

Climate Data Operators (CDO) is a collection of over 400 operators, developed and maintained by the Max-Planck-Institute for Meteorology, for post processing climate simulation data [5].

The ESDM functionality was tested and verified in the context of this project.

To include the ESDM read and write features it is only necessary to replace the netCDF library with the ESDM library during the build phase. That can be done by simply linking to the ESDM library instead of the usual one. ESDM implements the same interface as netCDF and therefore the exchange did not require any changes to CDO. Some minor changes were required and made to the underlying libcdi library. These changes are available in all current libcdi versions [2].

With these changes in CDI, CDO is now capable of reading/writing and processing EDSM files which need to be prefixed with “esdm://”.

As libcdi is contained within CDO there is no separate Spack package available, while the repository for libcdi is available under:

<https://gitlab.dkrz.de/mpim-sw/libcdi>

Other work has been done on CDO in the time of the project. These include:

- a new testing suite for CDO
- some minor build process changes to accommodate the requirements for compiling cuda and acc related code
- several refactorings for related sections as well as a new system for declaring CDO command line options.

Most of these changes will not be visible for the regular user and were done to increase the maintainability and reliability of CDO, and are already in the latest release of CDO. GPU related changes are pending to be released with the GPU accelerated routines currently worked upon.

The CDO repository is publicly available under:

<https://gitlab.dkrz.de/mpim-sw/cdo>

CDO is also available as a spack package:

https://spack.readthedocs.io/en/latest/package_list.html#cdo

While the Documentation can be found here:

<https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/cdo/wiki/Cdo#Documentation>

4. ParaView

ParaView (<https://paraview.org/>) is the defacto-standard for interactive 3D rendering and analysis of large datasets. It is an open-source (BSD3) software developed by Kitware Inc. It comes with builtin netCDF support for a range of standard data layouts. For several years, DKRZ has developed and maintained a reader for the ICON model output based on the Climate Data Interface (CDI). In the course of ESIWACE2, DKRZ has extended this reader to be more generic and enable the loading of arbitrary cell-based grids, given a matching grid file is provided. These developments have been merged into the main development branch of ParaView, and are now part of the nightly builds of the main branch available at <https://www.paraview.org/download/>, thus ensuring sustainability of the developments beyond the project lifespan of ESIWACE2.

As described in ESIWACE2 Deliverable D4.1 [1], ParaView can read data from ESDM by simply injecting the ESDM libnetcdf via LD_PRELOAD.

In the context of online analysis, we have decided to use the YAC coupler developed at DKRZ (<https://dkrz-sw.gitlab-pages.dkrz.de/yac/>), and used in the ICON model. As a coupler, YAC is designed to transfer fields between different model components in an MPI MPMD setting, subsetting and remapping on the fly as desired. Attaching ParaView Catalyst via YAC has several major advantages over classic in-situ approaches.

1. The coupler provides a clean interface, separating any development on the in-situ analysis from development of the core model.
2. By providing component parallelism, we can better exploit the extreme parallelism of current and upcoming supercomputers.
3. With heterogeneous jobs, the visualisation software can be run on different hardware platforms than the simulation code itself, allowing better exploitation of upcoming specialized hardware solutions.
4. With the built-in subsetting and remapping support of YAC, we can pass reduced data into ParaView Catalyst, drastically reducing computational costs for handling of data *on the backside of Earth* or avoiding the processing of scales much smaller than a pixel in the visualisation.

In the course of this effort, we have developed python bindings for YAC, opening the path for processing in-situ fields with python, and thus opening the path to in-situ analysis for the entire python universe, including many of the currently used machine learning approaches. At the same time, it enables the use

of ESDM-enabled python as a data source for the in-situ processing chain. We are planning to continue the developments of the in-situ coupling via YAC in the BMBF project WarmWorld.

5. Summary

Testing and deployment of the developments has been performed on the most powerful systems accessible by the WP partners during the project (Mistral and Levante @DKRZ, Zeus @CMCC). However, their testing and deployment on tier0 EuroHPC systems was not possible due to delays in the delivery and access to the systems. Nevertheless, portability and deployment on different platforms has been addressed by relying on package management tools, which can simplify this process. In fact, both CDO and ParaView, and the related project developments, are available through the Spack HPC package manager, while Ophidia has been included in Spack as part of the activities performed during the project (https://spack.readthedocs.io/en/latest/package_list.html#).

6. References

- [1] Bethke, Eugen, Lawrence, Bryan, Kunkel, Julian, Pedro, Luciana, Hübbe, Nathanael, Massey, Neil, Cole, Jeff, Lister, Grenville, Wilson, Simon, Elia, Donatello, & Palazzo, Cosimo. (2021). D4.1 Advanced software stack for Earth system data. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4651493>
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